

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE APPLICATION OF MIRROR THERAPY AND KINESIOTAPING IN THE COMPLEX RESTORATION OF THE MOTOR FUNCTIONS OF THE UPPER AND LOWER EXTREMITIES AFTER ISCHEMIC STROKE

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of the effectiveness of the use of mirror therapy and kinesiотaping in the restoration of motor functions of affected limbs after an ischemic stroke.

Keywords: ischemic stroke, mirror therapy, kinesiотaping, rehabilitation.

Formulation of the problem

Stroke was and remains a global medical, social and economic problem in Ukraine and the world, because it leads to serious physical and mental consequences, disability and mortality of the population. According to the data of the Public Health Center of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine, about 17 million cases of stroke occur in the world per year, this is approximately one case every two seconds, in Ukraine - about 140,000 per year, and this is one case every four minutes. As for mortality, approximately six and a half million people die from stroke in the world, and in Ukraine about 50,000 per year [8]. In addition, it is worth noting that millions of people around the world, including in Ukraine, live with the consequences of strokes.

A stroke, as defined by the World Health Organization, is "rapidly developing clinical signs of localized (or general) brain dysfunction with symptoms lasting 24 hours or more or leading to death, with no obvious etiology other than vascular origin" [4]

Ischemic stroke is one of the most common cerebrovascular diseases [5]. Ischemic stroke is an acute violation of cerebral blood circulation that occurs as a result of acute ischemia of the brain and is accompanied by structural and morphological changes in brain tissues and persistent organic neurological symptoms [9].

Ischemic strokes, characterized by blockage of blood vessels in the brain or neck, cause about 80% of all cases of the disease. Three conditions lead to this blockage: 1) thrombosis — the formation of a clot in a blood vessel of the brain; 2) embolism — the movement of a clot from another part of the body (for example, from the heart) to the brain; 3) stenosis — serious narrowing of an artery in the brain [11]. With the aging of society, personal underlying diseases (such as hypertension, diabetes, heart disease, and hyperhomocysteinemia), smoking, alcohol consumption, and other factors, the incidence of IS has been continuously rising [5].

The main stroke risk factors are:

- Age. Stroke occurs in all age groups, but the risk of the disease increases between the ages of 55 and 85.
- Sex. Men have a higher risk of stroke in young and middle age, but more women die of stroke in old age.
- Family medical history. Family members may have a genetic predisposition to risk factors for stroke: diabetes, hypertension, etc.

- High blood pressure / hypertension. Hypertension leads to a 2-4 times increase in the risk of stroke under the age of 80.

- Smoking. Cigarette smoking doubles the risk of ischemic stroke and increases the probability of hemorrhagic stroke by 4 times.

- Heart diseases. Coronary heart disease, valve defects, atrial fibrillation, and enlargement of one of the heart's chambers can lead to blood clots that can rupture and block blood vessels in the brain.

- Presence of transient ischemic attacks.

- Diabetes. Causes destructive changes in blood vessels throughout the body, particularly in the brain. If the blood glucose level is high during a stroke, then the brain damage is usually more severe than when the blood glucose is normal.

- Cholesterol imbalance. When cholesterol accumulates in the blood vessels, it leads to atherosclerosis. Atherosclerosis is the main cause of narrowing of blood vessels, which leads to both heart attack and stroke.

- Physical inactivity and obesity. Obesity and inactivity lead to hypertension, diabetes and heart disease [11].

The high level of stress in the population in connection with the full-scale war is also a provoking factor in the occurrence of strokes in Ukraine.

The purpose of the study: to substantiate the need for mirror therapy and kinesiотaping in the complex restoration of motor functions of the limbs after an ischemic stroke.

Research goals:

1. Determine the features of ischemic stroke and its consequences.

2. Compile an algorithm of rehabilitation measures for people with an ischemic stroke.

The main manifestations of a stroke: sudden deterioration of vision in one or both eyes, confusion with the pronunciation and understanding of words, sudden numbness in the body, face, limbs mostly on one side of the body, loss of coordination and balance of the body, severe headache for no apparent reason, loss of control over limbs, inability to raise both arms at the same time [1]

Symptoms and signs of an ischemic stroke depend on the affected part of the brain. Patterns of neurologic deficits often suggest an involved artery, but the correlation is often imprecise (Table 1) [7].

Table 1

Selected stroke syndromes	
Symptoms and signs	Syndromes
Contralateral hemiparesis (maximum in legs), urinary incontinence, apathy, confusion, poor judgment, mutism, grasping reflex, apraxia of gait	Anterior cerebral artery (infrequent)
Contralateral hemiparesis (worse in arms and face than legs), dysarthria, hemianesthesia, contralateral homonymous hemianopia, aphasia (if dominant hemisphere affected) or apraxia and sensory non-recognition (if non-dominant hemisphere affected)	Middle cerebral artery (common)
Contralateral homonymous hemianopia, unilateral cortical blindness, memory loss, unilateral 3rd cranial nerve palsy, hemibolism	Posterior cerebral artery
Monocular vision loss (amaurosis)	Ophthalmic artery (branch of the internal carotid artery)
Unilateral or bilateral cranial nerve deficits (eg. nystagmus, vertigo, dysphagia, dysarthria, diplopia, blindness), trunk or limb ataxia, spastic paresis, cross-sensory and motor disturbances*, impaired consciousness, coma, death (if basilar artery occlusion full), tachycardia, labile blood pressure	Vertebrobasilar system
Absence of cortical deficits plus one of the following:	Lacunar heart attacks
* Ipsilateral loss of facial sensation or motor weakness with contralateral hemianesthesia or hemiparesis of the body indicates involvement of the pons or medulla oblongata.	

Secondary post-stroke complications after a stroke are pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, post-stroke epilepsy, apalic syndrome, pelvic dysfunction, contractures, tendency to falls, mental and social maladaptation, sleep disorders, isolation syndrome[6].

Physical rehabilitation is an integral component in the process of restoring functioning, maintaining health, restoring functions, forming compensations, improving self-care, reducing dependence on outside help, and returning to a full life.

The main method of rehabilitation of stroke patients with movement disorders is physical therapy (kinesiotherapy), which aims to restore (full or partial) range of motion, strength and dexterity in the affected limbs, balance function, and self-care skills [10].

It is advisable to use kinesiotherapy in combination with kinesiotaping and mirror therapy.

Based on research results Azici G., Guclu-Gunduz A., Bayraktar D., Aksoy S., Nazliel B., Kilinc M., Yildirim S.A., Irkec C [2]. kinesio taping improves the transmission of sensorimotor signals, when applied to the ankle joint an improvement in postural stability was observed. The advantages of kinesio taping are non-invasiveness and duration of action. This method is effective in the treatment of paralysis and paresis, it changes the bioelectric activity in the muscles, thereby reducing spasticity in the affected limb due to neuroreflex mechanisms.

Various mirror neuron-based approaches can be used to restore hand function, namely mirror therapy (MT), action observation (AO), and motor imagery (MI)[12].

MI is a mental rehearsal of the physical movement of a body part. MI-based neurorehabilitation can be used at all stages of stroke recovery and is an adjunct to traditional rehabilitation that improves motor function[3,12].

MT is widely used as a method of rehabilitation. A mirror in the patients' midsagittal plane can reflect the movements of the patients' unaffected limbs super-

imposed on the position of the affected limbs, and create the visual illusion that the affected limbs of the patients can move normally [13]. MT is used to reduce pain, as well as to restore motility of affected limbs. AO is the therapy of observing the everyday actions of others, then the observer's own neural networks react as if a physical action is being performed.

Comprehensive rehabilitation aims and includes:

1. Early start of rehabilitation measures, individual approach and selection of exercises for each patient, continuous and phased use of rehabilitation means, their complex combination, control over performance and control of adequacy of physical load.

2. The rehabilitation program includes the use of kinesiotherapy, breathing exercises, massage, kinesiotaping and mirror therapy.

3. Exercises are performed under the supervision of a physical therapist.

4. Physical activity is dosed according to the patient's condition, his well-being, movement regime and stage of rehabilitation.

5. Positioning of the patient and changing the position of the body is used to avoid pathological postures and bedsores.

6. The main tasks of rehabilitation are: reducing the tone in spasmodic muscles, increasing muscle strength, expanding the amplitude of movements in the joints of the affected limbs, improving the clarity of the execution of movements, training balance and coordination from different starting positions, training the grasp of objects and their movement. support and improvement of basic motor skills and self-care skills. In order to perform these tasks, passive exercises, passive-active exercises, stretching exercises, active exercises, physical exercises from different starting positions, exercises for balance and coordination of movements, exercises for training fine motor skills are performed.

7. Respiratory gymnastics is used to improve the functional state of the respiratory and cardiovascular systems, engages the body's reserve forces, improves

microcirculation and exchange processes, thereby preventing pulmonary complications and stagnation in the body.

8. Performing exercises with a healthy limb while looking at its reflection in a mirror (mirror therapy) helps restore motor functions by forming the principle of feedback.

9. Kinesio taping is effective for stabilizing the muscles and ligaments of the affected limbs and for reducing the tone of spasmed muscles.

10. An important aspect in recovery is the active participation of the patient in the rehabilitation process, personal motivation and desire to work for the result.

Conclusions: So, we can say that movement is the basis of recovery of lost motor functions after an ischemic stroke.

Involvement of mirror therapy contributes to the transmission of impulses to the central nervous system and vegetative centers, as a result of which metabolic and redox processes are improved, the so-called mirror neurons are included in the work, motor activity improves. Kinesio taping helps to stabilize the musculoskeletal apparatus, reduces pain syndromes, normalizes blood circulation and lymph drainage, facilitates the performance of movements in the limbs and increases their amplitude.

The use of mirror therapy and kinesiointaping in complex rehabilitation after an ischemic stroke has a positive effect and accelerates the recovery of motor functions of the affected limbs.

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